

OPRAVIDLO 2.0: AI-POWERED PROOFREADER FOR CZECH TEXTS

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Topic

- spelling/grammar/typography correction service for Czech

Goals

- improve precision
- preserve explainability

Data

- publish correction rules with standard classification (ERRANT)
- publish a pseudonymized benchmark for Czech texts correction

Řekli nám, že pes je velmi klidný, a že je vhodný k dětem.

[They told us that the dog is very calm and suitable for children.]

klidný; → klidný

Extra sentence comma: an unnecessary comma is present

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Partneři se znechuceně po dlouhé hádce rozešli.

[The partners broke up in disgust after a long argument.]

Subject-predicate agreement error: the predicate does not agree with the subject

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From Beta Opravidlo...

- released in mid-2022
- rule-based system (7200 rules)
- covers errors in
 - spelling
 - grammar, punctuation
 - typography

adopted by users of Czech

- native speakers
- language learners

used for formal Czech texts:

- essays, schoolwork
- official documents, contracts
- CVs, presentations

Strong points

- high precision
- explainability

Weak points

- limited extensibility
- low recall
- processing speed

... to AI-powered Public Service

Plans

- free public service
- connection to Switchboard or other pipeline tool
- explanations in multiple languages
- fast and economic ensemble of rule-based and encoder-based models

Partial Results

Punctuation	Precision	Recall
RobeCzech-base	94.5	91.8
XLM-RoBERTa-large	98.5	75.8

- UI in multiple languages
- users can suggest new words

Challenges

- explainability for native speakers and language learners
- deployment on GPUs
- long-term sustainability
- personal information protection

Summary

Project contributions

- free public service for Czech proofreading
- fosters inclusivity within Czechia
- economic and long-term deployment
- FAIR data available for research

Future work

- provide encoder-based model(s) for the correction of long-range grammar phenomena
- preserve explainability
- publish ;-)

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